

Search string for PubMed

Items	Specification
Date of search	September 20, 2024
Databases	PubMed
Search terms used	<p>Concept 1: "Hernia, Femoral"[Mesh] OR "Hernia, Inguinal"[Mesh] OR ((groin OR femoral OR inguinal) AND (Hernia OR Hernias))</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Concept 2: "Herniorrhaphy"[Mesh] OR "Laparoscopy"[Mesh] OR "TAPP" OR (transabdominal AND (preperitoneal OR pre- peritoneal)) OR "TEP" OR ((total OR totally) AND (extraperitoneal OR extra-peritoneal))OR laparoscop* OR endoscop* OR laparoendoscop*</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Concept 3: ("Surgical Mesh"[Mesh] OR mesh) AND (fixation OR "Surgical Fixation Devices"[Mesh] OR tack* OR staple* OR glue OR sealant*)</p>
Timeframe	2015 – 2024